

GUIDELINES

These guidelines serve as a tool of support to the training activities planned by the European project “**Uptake ICT2life-cycle: digital literacy and inclusion to learners with disadvantaged background**”. They will be used as a guide for at least two types of actors involved in the project:

1. Trainers of trainers
2. Trainers of disadvantaged groups

Every project partner will have to follow the instructions provided in this document in order to structure both the first phase of the training of trainers and the second one of the training of the disadvantaged groups.

PHASE 1 TRAINING OF TRAINERS

DURATION: start date _____ closing date _____

CRITERIA FOR SELECTION OF EDUCATORS TO BE TRAINED

Educators with at least one of the following requirements should be selected:

1. Bachelor in the Education or Communication Science
2. Postgraduate title in the project themes
3. Professional experience as an educator in the same area documented

Every project partner can select the number of educators to be trained in this phase starting from a minimum of 5. It is advised to select educators from different geographical areas who already work with the disadvantaged groups in technologically equipped contexts.

TRAINING STRUCTURE

- The first meeting of socialization within the European project: researchers identified by each partner meet with the future trainers selected and present the European project illustrating the training scheme planned for them and for the disadvantaged groups for which they will be responsible in future.
The first meeting will be the only one with physical presence, as all the rest of the training of trainers will happen exclusively in the online environment.
- Training online:
 1. Treatment of topics at three levels of the course: basic, intermedium and advanced with specific focus on the instruments to be used (Gmail, Prezi, Animoto, Google Hangouts, WordPress, Mobincube).

Basic level:

Topics (modules):

- Turning on and off a PC safely
- Producing texts at the computer
- How to do a research of images
- How to create an email account - Gmail
- How to send and receive email messages through Gmail
- How to share contents safely

Intermedium level:

Topics (modules):

- How to produce and publish a dynamic presentation online (Prezi)
- How to create, edit and cut-edit a video (Animoto)
- How to manage a conversation space (chat) or a videoconference and participate in a forum (Google Hangouts)

Advanced level:

Topics (modules):

- How to create and publish a website (WordPress)
 - How to create an application (Mobincube)
2. Management and co-design of activities in class with the disadvantaged groups: trainers will learn how to manage the in class education with the disadvantaged groups from the first encounter. They will have at their disposal “canvas” to use at every meeting in class, which contain theoretical arguments to explain,

exercises and individual and group work to be assigned to the course participants, as well as the tools for assessing the acquired competencies.

During the phase of online training of trainers, at least one researcher identified by a partner will always be available and present. The role of the researcher in the online training environment will be to:

- Direct the training and set the pace and the ways of use of the online modules with support from tools like the calendar and the forum;
- Moderate discussions within the forum (and resolve doubts which emerge eventually);
- Send recall messages based on the timeline decided for the course (deadlines planned for using the modules, finishing exercises and doing tests);
- Remind and recall in case of delay in submissions;
- Verify the correctness of exercises by providing individual feedback

At the end of the training of trainers, a report will be made on the activities co-designed for every MOOC and the corresponding tools for observation and assessment which can be used for group trainings.

3. Sharing of tools of assessment of the learning and of customer satisfaction which can be used in the next phase

The educational online environment created for the training of trainers will have a twofold function: 1. to effectively train educators before their field intervention; 2. to follow up on the second phase of the training of the disadvantaged groups in order to share materials, ideas and collaborate online in the search for shared solutions.

PHASE 2: FORMATION OF THE DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

DURATION: Starting on _____ ending on _____

SELECTION CRITERIA FOR THE GROUPS

Every trained educator will have to identify at least one group of disadvantaged subjects to whom education on digital competences will be proposed.

Each disadvantaged group will have to start the education at the basic level in order to arrive to the advanced one by passing through the intermediate one.

In relation to the concept of disadvantage, its definition is contained within the project document “Uptake ICT”: “Particular attention will be given to the subjects of different age who have never used Internet and who are experiencing disadvantages (educational obstacles, social and geographical limits). Within the lifelong learning, the project aims to support individuals facing processes of civic change (social, political, economic and cultural), as well as to:

- Identify and share good practices of innovation for the society (digital alphabetization and inclusion);
- Develop basic and transversal competencies;
- Ensure equity in the realization of human rights especially in order to help the citizens who are living in disadvantaged contexts (socially or geographically) to integrate ICT in their lives;
- Riqualfication and updating of competencies;
- Dissemination of the research results (in different ways), promotion of the impact of ICT, sustainability, dissemination and use in the areas of science, society technology, politics and market/economy.

There are 2 key priorities of the project:

1. Contribute to reducing the number of adults who are not very competent (requalification and updating of their competencies)
2. Develop a partnership between education and development

Three key concepts are related to:

1. Access dimension for disadvantaged subjects
2. ICT and digital competencies
3. Key competencies and basic competencies

Each group will consist of at least 10 participants. In order to assess the level of competence, each group will have an entrance exam on the digital competences in order to clarify that there is a lack of competence at the beginning ([Annex - Entrance test](#)).

STRUCTURE OF THE EDUCATIONAL PATH

The educational path in this phase will be structured in three levels: basic, intermedium and advanced. At the end of each level, a test on the digital competence will be provided in order to assess the efficiency of the education. All the meetings (each one of 4 hours) will be held face-to-face in the places identified by the educators or agreed with the national project partner.

BASIC LEVEL

Topics of the modules:

- Turning a PC on and off safely
- Producing text on the computer
- How to do a research of images
- How to create a Gmail account
- How to send and receive emails through Gmail
- How to share contents safely

Basic activities to be done for each module:

- Theoretical description of what we will learn
- Image or a tutorial explaining the topic
- Exercises (undertake action, put in practice what one has learned by providing feedback online whenever possible)

The educator will, thus, organize his/her educational intervention in the way that the first phase contains face-to-face lessons at which he/she introduces and explains in-depth the topic of the module. Afterwards, he/she will go on to the second phase which is practical, as the group will then have to put into practice the knowledge and competences just acquired.

The scheme that follows illustrates this process through meetings held during the basic level.

MEETINGS	TOPIC	ANNEXES ON THE ACTIVITIES	EXCERCISES
first meeting	Turn on and off a PC safely; produce texts on the computer	ANNEX 1 ANNEX2	Individual excercises related to turning on and off the PC and producing texts on the PC.
Second meeting	How to do a research of images	ANNEX 3	Group exercise: conduct a research of images based on one or more topics proposed by the educator.
Third meeting	How to create an email account – Gmail; how to send and receive emails with Gmail	ANNEX 4 ANNEX 5	Individual work: simulate a creation of a Gmail account and exercise sending messages.
Fourth meeting	How to share contents safely	ANNEX 6	Individual work on the safety of the contents.

At the end of the basic level, the participant will produce work which valorizes the acquired competencies.

E.g. a Gmail account with personalization of the:

- Topic
- Labels
- Special conversations
- Calendar
- Contacts

Or a Word text with images to be sent to the teacher through the personal Gmail account.

INTERMEDIUM LEVEL

Topics of the modules:

1. How to produce and publish a dynamic presentation online (Prezi)
2. How to create, edit and cut-edit a video (Animoto)
3. How to manage a conversation space (chat) or a videoconference and participate in a forum (Google Hangouts)

The educator will, thus, organize his/her educational intervention in the way that the first phase contains face-to-face lessons at which he/she introduces and explains in-depth the topic of the module. Afterwards, he/she will go on to the second phase which is practical, as the group will then have to put into practice the knowledge and competences just acquired.

The scheme that follows illustrates this process through meetings held during the intermedium level.

MEETINGS	TOPIC	ANNEXES ON THE ACTIVITIES	EXCERCISES
first meeting Second meeting	How to produce and publish a dynamic presentation online (Prezi)	ANNEX 1	Group work: How to produce and publish a dynamic presentation online (Prezi)
Third meeting Fourth meeting	How to create, edit and cut-edit a video (Animoto)	ANNEX 2	Group work: How to create, edit and cut-edit a video (Animoto)
Fifth meeting	How to manage a conversation space (chat) or a videoconference and participate in a forum (Google Hangouts)	ANNEX 3	Individual work: How to manage a conversation space (chat) or a videoconference and participate in a forum (Google Hangouts)

At the end of the intermedium level, the participant will produce work which valorizes the acquired competencies.

E.g. a Prezi presentation or a video made with Animoto

ADVANCED LEVEL

Topics of the modules:

1. How to create and publish a website (WordPress)
2. How to create an APP (Mobincube)

The educator will, thus, organize his/her educational intervention in the way that the first phase contains face-to-face lessons at which he/she introduces and explains in-depth the topic of the module. Afterwards, he/she will go on to the second phase which is practical, as the group will then have to put into practice the knowledge and competences just acquired.

The scheme that follows illustrates this process through meetings held during the advanced level.

MEETINGS	TOPIC	ANNEXES ON THE ACTIVITIES	EXCERCISES
first meeting	How to create and publish a website (WordPress)	ANNEX 1	Group work: How to create and publish a website (WordPress)
Second meeting			
Third meeting			
Fourth meeting	How to create an APP (Mobincube)	ANNEX 2	Group work: How to create an APP (Mobincube)
Fifth meeting			
Sixth meeting			

At the end of this advanced level, the participant will produce work which valorizes the acquired competencies.

E.g. Creation of a blog or an App